

Appendix A: Properties of the synthetic m12f galaxy

This section provides auxiliary plots to aid in understanding the nature and properties of the synthetic m12f galaxy. The synthetic galaxy's surrounding distributions of dark matter, gas, and stellar particles are illustrated in Fig. A.1. The morphology of the galaxy and the kinematic distribution of its stellar particles are shown in Fig. A.2, with an indication of the volume of the galaxy probed by samples A, B, C, and D. Figure A.3 illustrates the geometric effects of the VM criterion in discerning the VM_{disk} from the VM_{halo} .

Fig. A.1. Face-on view of the synthetic galaxy m12f at redshift $z = 0$, zoomed out and color-coded according to the number of simulation particles per pixel. X and Y are cartesian coordinates of distance. **Left:** Distribution of dark matter particles. **Middle:** Distribution of gas particles. **Right:** Distribution of stellar particles.

Fig. A.2. Morphology and kinematics of the synthetic m12f galaxy at redshift $z = 0$, color-coded according to the number of stellar particles per pixel. Red circles indicate the spherical volume sampled in this work. **Left:** Face-on view of the galaxy. **Center Left:** Edge-on view of the galaxy. **Center Right:** Toomre diagram, where $\{U, V, W\}$ are the left-handed radial, azimuthal and vertical velocities. **Right:** Toomre diagram of the stellar particles contained within the volume enclosed by the red circles.

Fig. A.3. The synthetic m12f galaxy as seen edge-on, as well as subdivided into the VM_{disk} , VM_{halo} and $VM_{\text{Not Classified}}$ components according to the VM selection criterion, color-coded according to the number of stellar particles per pixel.

Appendix B: Properties of the synthetic stellar samples

This section highlights key features of samples A, B, C, and D. A comparison between sample A, samples B/C/D and the TESS seismic red-giant catalog is shown in Fig. B.1, demonstrating how samples B, C, and D replicate the sky coverage and parameter space of the TESS sample. The effect of reddening is observed in the HR diagram of the TESS sample in the form of a tilted red clump. The ν_{\max} parameter is not included in the synthetic samples, with the values provided here being estimated via a seismic scaling relation. Figure B.2 illustrates the effects of perturbing the stellar ages, chemical abundances and kinematics for samples C and D, with sample B as the reference. The histograms of the input parameters are provided in Fig. B.3, highlighting the deviation between sample A and samples B, C and D. We note that sample A has a large number of very young stars, which correlates with higher [Fe/H], lower $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ and a tighter distribution of azimuthal velocity, V , around V_{LSR} .

Fig. B.1. Comparison of sample A with the TESS sample and with samples B, C and D. **Top:** Sky coverage in declination and right-ascension. **Middle:** The frequency of maximum oscillation power (ν_{\max}) versus effective temperature (T_{eff}). **Bottom:** HR diagram showing the red-giant branch and the red clump.

Fig. B.2. Deviation of the perturbed values of stellar age, chemical abundance and kinematics for samples C and D relative to the true values of sample B. The kinematic values for samples C and D are extracted directly from the Ananke *Gaia* DR3-like survey and are therefore similar.

Fig. B.3. Histograms of the distributions of the stellar ages, chemical abundances and kinematics for samples A, B, C and D.

Appendix C: UMAP results

Figures C.1 and C.2 display the UMAP embeddings for MC1 and MC2, respectively, for each of the samples, color-coded according to the stellar ages, chemical abundances and kinematics used as input parameters. The distributions of the input parameters for samples A, B, C, and D, color-coded according to the UMAP runs are presented in Figs. C.3 (Toomre diagram), C.4 ($[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ vs $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$) and C.5 (stellar ages vs $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$).

Fig. C.1. UMAP embeddings for the major component MC1 of samples A, B, C and D, color-coded according to the input parameters.

Fig. C.2. UMAP embeddings for the major component MC2 of samples A, B, C and D, color-coded according to the input parameters.

Fig. C.3. Toomre diagram for samples A, B, C and D. **Top:** No color-coding is applied. **Middle:** Color-coded according to the major components found in the first run of UMAP. **Bottom:** Color-coded according to the subcomponents found in the second run of UMAP.

Fig. C.4. $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ versus $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ for samples A, B, C and D. **Top:** No color-coding is applied. **Middle:** Color-coded according to the major components found in the first run of UMAP. **Bottom:** Color-coded according to the subcomponents found in the second run of UMAP.

Fig. C.5. Stellar ages versus $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ for samples A, B, C and D. **Top:** No color-coding is applied. **Middle:** Color-coded according to the major components found in the first run of UMAP. **Bottom:** Color-coded according to the subcomponents found in the second run of UMAP.

Appendix D: UMAP versus other algorithms

In this section, we compare UMAP with other unsupervised machine learning algorithms to highlight its advantages. If we apply the HDBSCAN optimization routine directly to the 5D input parameter space, we obtain the results shown in Fig. D.1. For samples A and D, the clustering algorithm finds two clusters. In the case of sample A, one of the clusters appears to capture the disk, whereas the other appears to capture a portion of the halo, categorizing all other stars as outliers. For sample D, one of the clusters appears to capture the disk, with the other cluster capturing a very small and sparse group of old stars, further classifying nearly all stars in the halo as outliers. For samples B and C, the algorithm failed to converge, i.e., it did not return more than a singular valid cluster. We follow this up with a demonstration of the results for PCA and t-SNE.

Fig. D.1. Results obtained from the application of the HDBSCAN clustering algorithm directly to the 5D input parameter space. Obtained clusters are shown in blue and green, with outliers in gray. Samples B and C failed to converge.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a widely used algorithm in unsupervised machine learning due to its speed, efficiency and deterministic results. The limitations of PCA become apparent when attempting to derive nonlinear inferences from the data, as it is only meant to handle linear cases. Furthermore, PCA’s primary function is to find the axis with the highest variance, which is not necessarily useful when attempting to dissect highly entangled stellar populations. To test the performance of this method, we computed the two main principal components for samples A, B, C and D, and subsequently ran the HDBSCAN optimization routine. The results obtained are displayed in Figs. D.2 and D.3. For sample A, we obtain two small clusters that seem to represent old disk stars with a very narrow distribution in $\sqrt{U^2 + W^2}$, classifying the remainder sample stars as outliers. These clusters represent only a fraction of the high- α disk and do not correspond to two distinct stellar populations. For the remaining samples, the clustering algorithm failed to converge.

In UMAP, the latent space is initialized with a spectral embedding that is then refined using a stochastic gradient descent to optimize the positions of the points in the embedding space, such that both local and global structures are preserved. This results in efficient convergence towards a good representation of the data. A similar algorithm is the t-distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE), which iteratively minimizes the Kullback–Leibler (KL) divergence whilst constructing the latent space. The computational complexity of t-SNE is $O(n^2)$, making it less efficient than the $O(n \log n)$ complexity of UMAP. However, the Barnes–Hut t-SNE, which is an implementation of t-SNE that speeds its efficiency to $O(n \log n)$ complexity. Running t-SNE on the same standardized input parameters and then applying the HDBSCAN optimization routine returns the results shown in Figs. D.4 and D.5. For sample A, we obtain two distinct clusters, one of which appears to represent the disk and the other the halo. Despite sample B being pristine, the clustering algorithm fails to distinguish between the disk and the halo, converging instead to a solution that agglomerates the vast majority of stars into a single cluster, with a smaller cluster capturing a set of high-[Fe/H], low-[α /Fe] stars. This latter cluster does not constitute a stellar population. For samples C and D, we obtain once again a dominant cluster that captures the vast majority of the stars, with some small clusters that capture high-[Fe/H] stars with extreme (relative to that of the disk) [α /Fe] content.

A final comparison of the performances of t-SNE, UMAP and PCA is provided in Fig. D.6, comparing the 2D representations, the running time as a function of sample size and the trustworthiness score, $T(k = 15)$. Default hyperparameters were assumed

in all cases. PCA is evidently the fastest of the methods, but also the one displaying the lowest trustworthiness scores. Although UMAP and t-SNE have the same computational complexity, differences in their implementation lead to variations in the time taken to construct an embedding and in the efficiency of convergence, making UMAP faster than t-SNE. If we want to maximize fidelity with respect to the original input space, we should rely on t-SNE, which consistently outperforms UMAP. Maximizing fidelity does not necessarily equate to optimal clustering. If fidelity were the only priority, we would simply use the 5D input space, since it has, by definition, $T = 1 \forall k$. This is because t-SNE prioritizes preservation of local structure, whereas UMAP seeks to preserve both local and global structures, allowing for high trustworthiness scores and more efficient clustering, respectively.

Fig. D.2. Top: PCA analysis of samples A, B, C and D. Red dots correspond to ex situ stars ($d_{\text{form}} > 30$ kpc). **Bottom:** HDBSCAN clustering results. Samples B, C and D did not converge to more than one cluster and thus no clustering is provided.

Fig. D.3. Results obtained from the application of the HDBSCAN clustering algorithm to the space spanned by the two main principal components found by PCA. Obtained clusters are shown in blue and green, with outliers in gray. Samples B, C and D failed to converge.

Fig. D.4. Latent space embeddings generated by t-SNE for samples A, B, C and D. **Top:** Red dots correspond to ex situ stars ($d_{\text{form}} > 30$ kpc). **Bottom:** Clusters found by HDBSCAN.

Fig. D.5. Results obtained from the application of the HDBSCAN clustering algorithm to the 2D t-SNE latent space embeddings. Outliers are shown in gray.

Fig. D.6. Comparison of the algorithms Barnes–Hut t-SNE (in blue), UMAP (in red) and PCA (in green). Default hyperparameters were assumed in all cases, with 10,000 iterations adopted for t-SNE and UMAP. The algorithms were applied to randomly selected stars with input parameters $\{V, U, W, [\text{Fe}/\text{H}], [\alpha/\text{Fe}], \tau\}$ scaled with `StandardScaler`. **Top:** 2D spaces spanned by the t-SNE latent space embedding, the UMAP latent space embedding and the two main principal components, respectively. **Bottom:** The leftmost plot depicts the time needed to run each algorithm as a function of the sample size. Note the logarithmic scale in the x -axis. The center plot depicts the trustworthiness score, $T(k = 15)$, for the three algorithms applied to samples A, B, C and D.